

SECTION OF HUMANITIES AND PHILOLOGY

THE EVOLUTIONARY PATH OF THE BANDONEON IN MUSICAL ART

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Abstract

The victorious path of the bandoneon from a local instrument to a widespread performer of Argentine tango is demonstrable in the development of musical art.

Unfortunately, despite the unusual sound and compactness of the bandoneon, it did not become the subject of in-depth research. The largest range of research is observed in regions where bandoneon is widespread enough. These are Germany, Argentina, Uruguay.

At the same time, the evolutionary path of the bandoneon in the art of music is still chaotically covered in separate world studies, which requires systematization and deepening.

The purpose of the article is to consider the evolutionary path of the bandoneon in musical art, to carry out a historical retrospective of the spread of the bandoneon, to systematize its historical development.

The application of the historical-chronological method (to consider the stages of the spread of the art of bandoneon), axiological (to determine the value of the development of the art), systematization (when determining the stages of the development of the art of bandoneon) helped in determining the methodology of this study.

It was determined that the bandoneon is a keyboard-wind reed musical instrument, which is a type of hand harmonica. Named after its promoter, Heinrich Band. More than 200 years have passed since its appearance. Traditionally, the Argentine spread of the bandoneon is considered, recognizing Germany as the homeland of the instrument. The bandoneon was invented around 1830 by K.F. Uhlig from Chemnitz. But this interpretation is controversial, which is also explored in the article. Based on a review of literary sources, the evolutionary path of the bandoneon in musical art is considered.

The use of the historical-chronological method and the method of systematization during the research contributed to the implementation of a historical retrospective of the spread of bandoneon, systematization of its historical development.

The scientific novelty of the research is determined as follows. The evolutionary path of the bandoneon in musical art was formed, a historical retrospective of the spread of the bandoneon was carried out, and its historical development was systematized. Thus, the goal of the research has been achieved.

Further directions of scientific research are determined to clarify the role and influence of outstanding bandoneon players on the historical development of bandoneon.

Keywords: bandoneon, harmonica, diatonic instrument, keyboard and wind reed musical instrument, concertina, bandoneon art, musical art, musical instruments, chromatic instrument.

Formulation of the problem. The infinite, incalculable multitude of musical instruments around the world testifies to society's profound affinity for the art of music. «Music possesses the same global language that creates an atmosphere of friendly and harmonious relations among people... Knowledge of different traditions, customs, and cultures plays an important role...» [1].

The triumphant journey of the bandoneon from a local instrument to a widely performed one in Argentine tango is indicative in the above-mentioned context. Many Ukrainian experts, while studying the art of music, focus their attention on various instruments.

Analysis of recent research and publications. The study of the contribution of bandura players from Galicia to the development of bandura art is dedicated to the research of V. Dutchak [2].

The examination of the works of the renowned guitarist-composer Antonio Lauro and the virtuoso Alirio Díaz in the context of the formation and development of the Venezuelan guitar school of the 20th century is the subject of works by T. Ivannikov and T. Filatova [3; 4]. They systematically worked in the field of

Venezuelan guitar art, particularly investigating the cuatro as a historical phenomenon in Venezuelan guitar art. Works by V. Myshalov are devoted to bandura performance [5].

Significant attention is focused on the piano/fortepiano and prominent pianists in the works of I. Dovzhenko, N. Kengerli-Nadjafova [6; 7]. The figure of the composer, educator, and pianist Konstantin Franzovich von Feist is examined in I. Dovzhenko's work [6].

The development of the oboe school is studied by L. Zakopets [8]. V. Dutchak and I. Ryabchun have concentrated their efforts on the history, sound production specifics, and philosophy of performance possibilities of the carillon—a European musical instrument that has gained active popularity in Ukraine in recent decades [9].

Research on a range of string instruments is dedicated to N. Feshchak [10].

Highlighting previously unresolved parts of the overall problem. However, the majority of aspects related to the bandoneon remain overlooked by researchers. Despite its unique sound and compactness, the bandoneon has not been the subject of in-depth investigations. Certain aspects of playing the bandoneon and

general questions about its historical origins have been studied, but mainly within the framework of other scientific issues. These include the emergence of schools, the generalized aspect of establishing performance schools, and the educational-methodological principles of the modern bandoneon school.

Most of these studies are not Ukrainian works but rather research conducted by global scholars and enthusiasts of the bandoneon, as well as professional makers and performers of Argentine tango. The most extensive research is observed in regions where the bandoneon is sufficiently widespread, such as Germany, Argentina, and Uruguay.

Along with that, the evolutionary path of the bandoneon in the field of musical art in the specified process currently remains chaotically illuminated in separate global studies, requiring systematization and deepening.

The goal of the article is to examine the evolutionary path of the bandoneon in musical art, conduct a historical retrospective of its dissemination, and systematize its historical development.

Methods. The application of the historical-chronological method (to examine the stages of the spread of the art of the bandoneon), axiological (to determine the value of the development of the art), and systematization (when determining the stages of the development of the art of the bandoneon) has helped define the methodology of this research.

Presentation of the main material. The bandoneon is considered a unique musical instrument with a distinctive origin and characteristic sound. It is significantly smaller than the accordion.

By N. Bratchuk's definition, «the Bandoneon is a reed-organ keyboard instrument, a type of manual harmonica» [11].

In the Ukrainian Wikipedia, «Bandoneon (Spanish: bandoneon) is a musical instrument, a type of harmonica. Named in honor of its inventor, Heinrich Band. Initially used for performing sacred music in German churches. In the late 19th century, it was imported to Argentina and became part of tango orchestras. It is thanks to the bandoneon that the music of Argentine tango acquired the poignant and touching sound that attracts so many admirers to it» [12].

According to the definition [13], the bandoneon (Spanish: bandoneon, German: Bandoneon, from Band – the inventor's surname, and (Akkord)eon – accordion) is a keyboard-reed musical instrument, a type of hand-held harmonica. It is particularly popular in Argentina and Uruguay, typical for most tango orchestras.

As evident from the definition, the bandoneon belongs to the types of hand-held harmonicas. Its invention dates back more than 200 years [14]. Its creation laid the groundwork for the development of the bayan, accordion, and harmonium.

Traditionally, the spread of the bandoneon is associated with Argentina, recognizing Germany as the instrument's place of origin.

The Great Ukrainian Encyclopedia (VUE) has the following expanded perspective [13]. «According to the main version, around 1840, the music instrument

seller and music teacher G. Bend (1821–1860; Germany) constructed the concertina based on the square German concertina as a diatonic, later chromatic instrument. According to other versions, around 1834, K. F. Uhlig (1789–1874; Germany) invented it in Chemnitz. G. Bend modified and expanded the original layout of the button panel, or instrument maker K. F. Zimmermann (1817; Germany – 1898; USA), who presented his invention at the Industrial Exhibition in Paris in 1849». G. Bend is recognized for promoting the instrument: from 1854, he organized its production and sales in Carlsfeld with specially written music. Initially, the instrument was known as the Carlsfeld Concertina, and the name «bandoneon» was formed in 1882 from Band's surname.

Initially used for performing religious music (as a substitute for the organ) in churches and small religious communities in Germany. However, the complexity of playing it hindered widespread adoption.

From the 1920s, it was used in popular music. Bandoneon orchestras became popular: the instruments were tuned as piccolo (an octave higher), normal, and bass (an octave lower). By 1939, there were already 686 similar orchestras in Germany.

At the end of the 19th century, the bandoneon was introduced to Uruguay and Argentina, where it became an integral part of tango orchestras. Experiencing a surge in popularity, it virtually displaced the accordion. From 1911, bandoneons were exclusively manufactured in Germany for the Argentine and Uruguayan markets (with 20 thousand units exported to Argentina alone in 1930).

The design of the instrument gradually evolved, and the number of tones increased to 142 (sometimes 152). It had 5 rows of buttons for the left hand and 6 rows for the right hand. At that time, the Spanish variant of the name also became established.

The destruction of German production during World War II led to the cessation of mass production of bandoneons. By the 2000s, vintage bandoneons had become rare and highly valued.

In 2014, the National University of Lanus in Argentina announced plans to develop an affordable bandoneon of Argentine production [13].

N. Doktorski believes that «the bandoneon, resembling a large square concertina, is another bellows instrument that until recently was rarely heard outside dance halls. Its origins are traced back to the concertina. Another development was the considerably larger bandoneon created by Heinrich Band (1821-1860), initially diatonic and later a fully chromatic instrument, especially popular in South America. However, Albert Beer asserted in Macmillan's Encyclopedia of Music and Musicians that the bandoneon was invented around 1830 by K. F. Uhlig from Chemnitz and was named after the musical instrument dealer from Krefeld, Heinrich Band» [15].

Adding to this, it should be noted that the development of the bandoneon was facilitated by its low manufacturing cost and affordability for low-income populations (the poor). «It was invented for people who did not belong to the upper class and did not have the

opportunity to take lessons from music teachers. However, music was still a vital for them. In their daily lives, they wanted to hear or play, for example, a melody from an opera aria». [16].

Some researchers need identify the concertina and the bandoneon as the same instrument. However, the concertina is significantly smaller and lighter than the bandoneon.

M. Shapiro believed that «there is evidence that it [the bandoneon] was actually invented by K. Zimmermann from Saxony, who introduced his invention to the world at the industrial exhibition in Paris in 1849. ... This instrument was known as the Carlsfelder Konzertina. In 1850, the merchant Heinrich Band announced the existence of this instrument. There are no records of him claiming to have invented it... However, in Krefeld, it became known as the bandoneon, probably as a fusion of his name and the accordion» [15].

«Dutch bandoneon maker Harry Geuns seemed to provide the most plausible explanation: in 1835, Karl Friedrich Uhlig from Chemnitz built the first German concertina (a large square instrument), unaware of the smaller octagonal English concertina by Wheatstone. Later, Karl Zimmermann and Heinrich Band released their own versions with different button layouts. Bend was an instrument dealer who did not manufacture his own instruments. Button panel layouts created by the three «builders» became known as the Rheinische (Band), Chemnitzer (Uhlig), and Carlsfelder (Zimmerman) systems» [15].

Based on a review of literary sources, the evolutionary path of the bandoneon in the musical arts is examined (Table 1), applying the axiological method of research.

Table 1

Systematization of the evolutionary path of the bandoneon in the musical arts

Possible inventor	Year of invention	Designer	Scheme of button panels
Karl Friedrich Ulig from Chemnitz, Germany, (1789–1874)	1835	Karl Friedrich Ulig	Chemnitzer (Uhlig)
Karl Friedrich Zimmermann from Karlsfeld, Saxony, Germany, (1817 – 1898)	1849	Karl Friedrich Zimmermann	Carlsfelder (Zimmerman)
Heinrich Band from Krefeld, Germany, (1821-1860)	1840	Heinrich Band	Rheinische (Band)

The use of the historical-chronological method and the method of systematization during the research contributed to the implementation of a historical retrospective of the spread of bandoneon, systematization of its historical development.

Table 2

A historical retrospective of the spread of the bandoneon

Stages	Years	Lynx
Occurrence	1835–1849	Possible inventors Karl Friedrich Uhlig, Karl Friedrich Zimmermann, Heinrich Band
Initial	1854–1882	Initially, it was used to perform sacred music (as a substitute for the organ) in churches and small religious communities in Germany
Conquest of the market	1854–1882	Bend's efforts significantly contributed to the conquest of the music market by the bandoneon
Creation of the "Bandoneon" brand	1882	The name «bandoneon» was formed in 1882 from the surname Banda and «accordion». In 1854, he organized its production and sale together with specially written music in Karlsfeld. A significant role of G. Band as a promoter of the instrument
Dissemination	the end of the 19th century	The bandoneon was brought to Argentina and Uruguay and became a part of tango orchestras
Filling the market	1911–...	Bandoneons were made in Germany exclusively for the market in Argentina and Uruguay (20,000 units were exported to Argentina in 1930 alone).
Adoption of a single system	1920s	Adoption of a single system, bandoneon orchestras became popular; the instruments were built in three sizes: piccolo (an octave higher), regular, and bass (an octave lower).
Distribution in Germany	1920–1939	There were 686 bandoneon orchestras in Germany
Destruction of German production	1949	The destruction of German production during World War II led to the end of mass production of bandoneons
The period of Astor Piazzolla	1931–1992	Performer-composer Astor Piazzolla took the bandoneon from the dance hall to the concert stage
Creating a classic bandoneon	After 1940	Argentine Alejandro Barletta (born 1925) is the father of the classical bandoneon
Production in Argentina	2014	The National University of Lanus in Argentina has announced plans to develop an affordable, Argentine-made bandoneon

Compiled by the author based on [15].

Compositions for the bandoneon are written for various combinations of guitar, violin, bandoneon, cello, piano, flute, and percussion; for violin, cello, flute, oboe, clarinet, percussion, and bandoneon; for bandoneon and orchestra; for oboe, bandoneon, and orchestra; for guitar, bandoneon, and orchestra; for violin, cello, bandoneon, and orchestra; and for an ensemble of four bandoneons.

It is emphasized once again that scholars consider «Music, as the most informative form of spiritual culture, also plays a significant role in the formation of self-esteem for the ethnic group and ethnic identification» [17]. Additionally, there is importance placed on virtuoso performance on the instrument [18].

Scientific novelty of the research. The evolutionary path of the bandoneon in the field of musical art has been traced, and a historical retrospective of the spread of the bandoneon has been conducted. Its historical development has been systematized. Thus, the goal of the research has been achieved.

Further research directions have been identified, including the clarification of the role and impact of prominent bandoneon players in the historical development of the instrument.

Conclusions. The victorious journey of the bandoneon from a local instrument to a widely performed instrument in Argentine tango illustrates its contribution to the development of musical art.

Unfortunately, despite its unusual sound and compactness, the bandoneon has not been the subject of in-depth research. The majority of studies focus on regions where the bandoneon is sufficiently prevalent, namely Germany, Argentina, and Uruguay.

Meanwhile, the evolutionary path of the bandoneon in musical art remains chaotically illuminated in separate global studies, requiring systematization and deeper exploration.

The goal of this article is to examine the evolutionary path of the bandoneon in musical art, provide a historical retrospective of its spread, and systematize its historical development.

It is determined that the bandoneon is a keyboard-reed free-reed musical instrument, a type of hand-held harmonica, named in honor of its promoter, Heinrich Band.

The scientific novelty of the research is determined as follows. An evolutionary path of the bandoneon in the field of musical art has been formed, a historical retrospective of the spread of the bandoneon has been carried out, and its historical development has been systematized. Thus, the research goal has been achieved.

Further directions of scientific inquiry include clarifying the role and impact of prominent bandoneonists on the historical development of the bandoneon.

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